

Melnikov Function Analysis of Chaos in a Parametrically Excited Morse Oscillator with Two Forcing Terms

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This paper focuses on the analysis of chaos using the Melnikov method in a linearly damped Morse oscillator subjected to two parametric forcing terms. The unperturbed Morse oscillator features a degenerate fixed point at infinity, which is resolved by applying a McGehee-type transformation. This transformation regularizes the stationary fixed point, making it possible to apply the Melnikov method effectively. By using the Melnikov analytical technique, we derive the threshold condition for the onset of horseshoe chaos. We analyze the effects of two parametric forces with frequencies $\Omega = \omega$ and $\Omega \neq \omega$ on the dynamics of the system. Due to the two parametric forces, we identify regions where chaos is either suppressed or enhanced, depending on the parametric choices. The analysis is carried out in terms of bifurcation diagrams, phase portraits, trajectory plots, and the time measure $1/\tau_M$. The results indicate that the system with two parametric forces exhibits rich dynamical behaviors, including multiple coexisting attractors, period-doubling bifurcations, period-bubbling, reverse period-doubling bifurcations, antimonotonicity (i.e., concurrent creation and annihilation of periodic orbits), and chaotic attractors.

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1. Introduction

Chaos is a well-established phenomenon in Hamiltonian dynamics. To analyze chaotic motion in perturbed nonlinear dynamical systems or identify the parameter regions where chaos occurs, the Melnikov technique [1-3] serves as a highly effective tool. This method provides an analytic criterion for chaos in weakly perturbed Hamiltonian systems [4]. The Melnikov function quantifies the transverse distance between the stable and unstable manifolds associated with an unstable periodic orbit. The presence of isolated odd zeros in the Melnikov function indicates transverse intersections of these manifolds,

marking the onset of chaos [2]. In recent years, this method has been applied to various nonlinear systems [5-12]. Furthermore, the Melnikov method has found applications in numerous branches of physics. Examples include its use in the study of Josephson junctions [13,14], planar periodic vertical flows [15], solitons [16], liquid crystals [17], quasiparticle transfer dynamics [18], and electromagnetic systems [19].

The Morse oscillator is a widely used model in quantum mechanics and molecular physics to describe the vibrational behavior of atoms in a diatomic molecule. It offers a significant improvement over the simple harmonic oscillator, which assumes the potential energy increases quadratically with displacement. In contrast, the Morse potential accounts for the anharmonic nature of molecular vibrations, particularly at large displacements where the harmonic oscillator approximation fails [20]. Numerous studies

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have investigated the Morse oscillator using classical, semiclassical, and quantum mechanical approaches [21-30]. Recently, Kyurkchiev [31] analyzed the dynamics of perturbed Morse-type oscillators using the Melnikov method. Lotliker et al. [32] conducted a detailed study on the performance of a newly modified Morse potential energy function for both ground and excited states of diatomic molecules. Ahmed et al. [33] examined the nonrelativistic bound state energy spectrum and persistent current in a modified Rosen-Morse oscillator confined to a two-dimensional electromagnetic potential field. Additionally, Marwan Al-Raei [34] derived an analytical formula for the Morse oscillator equation of state for systems described by the Morse potential in the vibrational case.

Motivated by these studies, this paper analyzes the occurrence of horseshoe chaos using the Melnikov perturbation technique in a linearly damped Morse oscillator with two parametric forces. The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 describes the model and provides an analysis of the unperturbed system. Section 3 derives the threshold condition for the onset of chaos using the Melnikov method. Numerical simulations are presented in Section 4, and conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Description of the model and analysis of the unperturbed system

This paper focuses on predicting the onset of chaos in a linearly damped Morse oscillator subjected to two parametric forces, represented by the equation

$$\dot{x} + \alpha \dot{x} - \beta (1 + f \sin \omega t + g \sin \Omega t) e^{-x} (e^{-x} - 1) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Here, x denotes the distance between the atoms, β is a constant parameter representing the dissociation energy, and the depth of the potential well is $\beta/2$. The parameter α is the damping coefficient, while f, ω , and g, Ω , represent the amplitudes and frequencies of the two parametric forces, respectively. Recently,

FIG. 1: The homoclinic orbit.

Sofroniou and Bishop [35] analyzed the dynamics of parametrically excited systems with two forcing terms. The potential function of the Morse oscillator is given by

$$V(x) = \frac{1}{2} \beta e^{-x} (e^{-x} - 2). \quad (2)$$

The unperturbed system is Hamiltonian, where the Hamiltonian function is given by

$$H(x, y) = \frac{y^2}{2} + \beta (-e^{-x} + \frac{1}{2} e^{-2x}) = h \quad (3)$$

Setting $\det(M - \lambda I) = 0$ to zero, we obtain the eigenvalues $\lambda_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{2\beta e^{-2x} - \beta e^{-x}}$. Both eigenvalues are zero at $(\infty, 0)$, making $(\infty, 0)$ a non-hyperbolic fixed point of Eq. (1). From the Hamiltonian $H(x, y)$ with a constant value h , the system satisfies $y = \pm \sqrt{2h - \beta (-2e^{-x} + e^{-2x})}$. The homoclinic orbit, corresponding to the solution for $h = 0$ is illustrated in Fig. 1.

3. Derivation of Melnikov function

The equation motion of parametrically excited Morse oscillator with two forcing terms is given by

$$\dot{x} = y, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{y} = \beta e^{-x} (e^{-x} - 1) + \epsilon (-\alpha \dot{x} + \beta (f \sin \omega t + g \sin \Omega t) e^{-x} (e^{-x} - 1)) = 0 \quad (5)$$

To apply the Melnikov method, the system (4),(5) must possess a non-degenerate fixed point. However, the unperturbed Morse oscillator

features a degenerate fixed point. This issue is resolved using a McGehee transformation [36], which removes the degeneracy of the fixed point at ∞ . Under this transformation, the parabolic orbit of the original system corresponds to a homoclinic orbit in the new coordinates. To regularize the fixed point $(\infty, 0)$, we perform the following coordinate transformation

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -2 \ln(u), \\ y &= v \\ \frac{ds}{dt} &= \frac{-u}{2}, \Rightarrow t(s) = -2 \int \frac{ds}{u(s)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The equation of the system in new coordinates, the Eqs. (4),(5) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{du}{ds} &= v. \\ \frac{dv}{ds} &= 2\beta u(1 - u^2) + \epsilon \left[\frac{2\alpha v}{u} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2\beta u(1 - u^2)f \sin(\omega t(s)) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2\beta u(1 - u^2)g \sin(\Omega t(s)) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The corresponding unperturbed system is,

$$\frac{du_0}{ds} = v_0, \quad \frac{dv_0}{ds} = 2\beta u_0(1 - u_0^2) \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) represents the unperturbed part of the Duffing oscillator, where the equilibrium point $(u_0^*, v_0^*) = (0, 0)$ is a non-degenerate fixed point. This fixed point is also hyperbolic, as the corresponding eigenvalues are given by $\det(M - \lambda I = 0 \implies \lambda_{1,2} = \pm\sqrt{2\beta}$, both of which have non-zero real parts. Consequently, the system is now suitable for applying the Melnikov method. In the new coordinates, the Hamiltonian is expressed as

$$I = \frac{v_0^2}{2} + \beta u_0^2 \left(\frac{u_0^2}{2} - 1 \right). \quad (10)$$

Rewriting Eq. (10), we obtain $v_0 = \pm\sqrt{2I - \beta u_0^2(u_0^2 - 2)}$. The homoclinic solution corresponds to $I = 0$. A plot of $v_0 = \pm\sqrt{2I - \beta u_0^2(u_0^2 - 2)}$ with $I = 0$ and $\beta = 1$ as a function of u_0 is shown in Fig. 2. The homoclinic bifurcation occurs when $I \neq 0$.

FIG. 2: The homoclinic solution with $\beta = 1$.

The analytical expression corresponds to homoclinic solution is given by

$$u_0(s, s_0) = \pm\sqrt{2} \operatorname{sech} \left(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0) \right), \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_0(s, s_0) &= \mp 2\sqrt{\beta} \operatorname{sech} \left(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0) \right) \\ &\quad \tanh \left(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

From Eq. (6), we can obtain the new parameterized time is

$$\begin{aligned} t(s, s_0) &= \tau - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta}} \left[\sinh(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0)) \right] \\ \Rightarrow t(s, s_0) &= \tau - \frac{s'}{\sqrt{\beta}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $s' = \sinh(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0))$ and τ is the constant of integration which corresponds to initial time.

For the calculation of Melnikov function, the method given in [37] is used. The Melnikov function is given by

$$M(\tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{X}_0^s I) ds \quad (14)$$

\hat{X}_0^s is the vector field of the perturbation which acts on the first integral I . From Eqs. (7),(8), the vector field of the perturbation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X}_0^s &= \left[\frac{2\alpha v_0}{(u_0)} + 2\beta u_0(1 - u_0^2)f \sin(\omega t(s, s_0)) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2\beta u_0(1 - u_0^2)g \sin(\Omega t(s, s_0)) \right] \frac{\partial}{\partial v_0} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Substituting the Eq. (15) in Eq. (14) and $\frac{\partial I}{\partial v_0} = v_0$, then Eq. (14) becomes,

$$\begin{aligned}
 M^\pm(\tau) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{X}_0^s I ds = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2\alpha v_0^2}{(u_0)} + 2\beta u_0 v_0 (1 - u_0^2) f \sin(\omega t(s, s_0)) + 2\beta u_0 v_0 (1 - u_0^2) g \sin(\Omega t(s, s_0)) \right] ds \\
 &= M_1 + M_2 + M_3
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2\alpha v_0^2}{u_0} \right] ds \\
 M_2 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} 2\beta u_0 v_0 (1 - u_0^2) f \sin(\omega t(s, s_0)) ds \\
 M_3 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} 2\beta u_0 v_0 (1 - u_0^2) g \sin(\Omega t(s, s_0)) ds
 \end{aligned}$$

With the substitution of $s' = \sinh(\sqrt{2\beta}(s - s_0))$ and Eqs. (11),(12), the integral value of M_1, M_2

and M_3 are given by

$$M_1 = 2\pi\alpha\sqrt{\beta} \tag{17}$$

$$M_2 = -\pi\sqrt{\beta}\omega f\left(\frac{\omega}{\sqrt{\beta}} - 1\right)e^{-\omega/\beta}\cos\omega\tau \tag{18}$$

$$M_3 = -\pi\sqrt{\beta}\Omega g\left(\frac{\Omega}{\sqrt{\beta}} - 1\right)e^{-\Omega/\beta}\cos\Omega\tau \tag{19}$$

Substituting the values of M_1, M_2 and M_3 in Eq. (16), then the Melnikov function becomes

$$M^\pm(\tau) = 2\pi\alpha\sqrt{\beta} \mp \pi\sqrt{\beta}\omega f\left(\frac{\omega}{\sqrt{\beta}} - 1\right)e^{-\omega/\beta}\cos\omega\tau \mp \pi\sqrt{\beta}\Omega g\left(\frac{\Omega}{\sqrt{\beta}} - 1\right)e^{-\Omega/\beta}\cos\Omega\tau. \tag{20}$$

4. Numerical simulations

This section presents numerical simulations to support the theoretical results obtained in the previous section and to explore additional complex dynamics. We first analyze the effect of two parametric forces on the dynamics of the system (4),(5) with the condition $\Omega = \omega$. The case where $\Omega \neq \omega$ is addressed in the next section.

4.1. Effect of two parametric forces with $\Omega = \omega$

The occurrence of horseshoe chaos for $\Omega = \omega$ is investigated by varying the control parameter f of the parametric forces, while keeping g fixed. Throughout this study, the other system parameters are fixed at $\alpha = 1.0$ and $\beta = 8.0$. Numerically, the occurrence of horseshoe

chaos can be studied by measuring the time τ_M elapsed between two successive transverse intersections. This time, τ_M , is determined from Eq. (20). Figure 3 illustrates the variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ with f for $\Omega = \omega = 6.0$ and $g = 0.7$. The continuous curve represents the inverse of the first intersection time ($1/\tau_M^+$) for the stable and unstable branches of the homoclinic orbits W^+ (corresponding to the positive sign of Eq. (20)), while the dashed curve corresponds to the orbits W^- (negative sign of Eq. (20)). Horseshoe dynamics do not occur when $1/\tau_M = 0$; they are observed only in regions where $1/\tau_M > 0$. In Fig.3, $1/\tau_M^\pm$ is zero for the interval $0 < f < 0.834992$ indicating no horseshoe chaos occurs in this range. For $f \geq 0.834992$, $1/\tau_M^\pm$ becomes non-zero, suggesting that horseshoe chaos is possible in these regions.

The above analytical results are further

FIG. 3: Variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus f for $\Omega = \omega = 6.0$. The continuous curve represents the positive sign of $M(\tau)$, and the dashed curve represents the negative sign of $M(\tau)$ as given by Eq. (20). The values of the other parameters in Eq. (20) are $g = 0.7, \alpha = 1.0$, and $\beta = 8.0$.

FIG. 4: (a) Bifurcation diagram of the system (4),(5) as a function of f with $g = 0.7$. (b) Magnification of a part of the bifurcation diagram from Fig.4(a). The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0$, and $\Omega = \omega = 6.0$.

validated through direct numerical simulations of the system (4),(5). The system was numerically integrated using a fourth-order Runge-Kutta method to investigate the occurrence of horseshoe chaos. Qualitative tools such as bifurcation diagrams, phase portraits, trajectory plots, and the measurement of time τ_M were employed to characterize various scenarios leading to chaos. By tuning the parameter f in the range

FIG. 5: Phase portraits of the system (4),(5) showing (a) the periodic orbit for $f = 0.2$ and (b) the chaotic orbit for $f = 0.95$. The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $g = 0.7, \alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0$, and $\omega = \Omega = 6.0$.

$0 \leq f \leq 2$, the bifurcation diagram of the local coordinate x is plotted in Fig. 4(a). For greater clarity, a magnified portion of the bifurcation diagram in Fig.4(a) is presented in Fig.4(b). As shown in Fig.4, the dynamics of the system (4),(5) exhibits periodic attractors, single-band chaotic attractors, and double-band chaotic attractors. The transition to chaos is observed through classical period-doubling bifurcations. Additionally, coexisting bifurcation modes are depicted in Fig. 4. For $g = 0.7$, the onset of chaos occurs at $f_c = 0.840934$. From Fig. 3, the onset of horseshoe chaos is observed at $f_M = 0.834992$. These numerical results are in good agreement with the analytical predictions

The results are further corroborated by phase portraits and trajectory plots, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Phase portraits for $f = 0.2$ (where $1/\tau_M < 0$) and $f = 0.95$ (where $1/\tau_M > 0$) are depicted in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. As expected, periodic behavior is observed for $f = 0.2$, while chaotic behavior occurs for $f = 0.95$. The trajectory plots for $f = 0.2$ and $f = 0.95$ are shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b). The presence of a uniform trajectory, as seen in Fig. 6(a) for $f = 0.2$, indicates periodic behavior. In contrast, the presence of maxima and minima in Fig. 6(b) for $f = 0.95$ is indicative of chaotic behavior. Once again, the numerical results align well with the analytical predictions, demonstrating consistency between theoretical and numerical approaches.

FIG. 6: Trajectory plots showing (a) the periodic orbit for $f = 0.2$ and (b) the chaotic orbit for $f = 0.95$. The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $g = 0.7, \alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0,$ and $\omega = \Omega = 6.0$.

FIG. 7: Variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus f for (a) $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$ and (b) $\Omega = \omega = 5.5$. The continuous curve represents the positive sign of $M(\tau)$, and the dashed curve represents the negative sign of $M(\tau)$ as given by Eq. (20). The values of the other parameters in Eq. (20) are $g = 0.7, \alpha = 1.0,$ and $\beta = 8.0$.

Next, we analyze the effect of $\Omega = \omega$ for two additional frequency values, $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$ and $\Omega = \omega = 5.5$. The corresponding analytical and numerical results are presented in Figs. 7 and 8. Figure 7 shows the variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ with f for two values of $\Omega(= \omega)$, with $g = 0.7, \alpha = 1.0,$ and $\beta = 8.0$. In Fig. 7(a), for $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$, horseshoe chaos does not occur in the range $0 < f < 0.580659$, as $1/\tau_M < 0$ in this interval. Horseshoe chaos is observed for $f \geq 0.580659$, where $1/\tau_M > 0$. Similarly, for $\Omega = \omega = 5.5$, periodic behavior is present in the interval $0 < f < 0.674036$, as indicated by $1/\tau_M < 0$. For $f \geq 0.674036$, $1/\tau_M > 0$, and horseshoe chaos is possible. These analytical findings are validated in Fig. 8. Figure 8 illustrates the bifurcation patterns for $\Omega(= \omega)$ values of 5.0 and 5.5. From Figs. 8(a)

FIG. 8: Bifurcation diagrams of the system (4),(5) as a function of f with (a) $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$ and (b) $\Omega = \omega = 5.5$. The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0,$ and $g = 0.7$.

FIG. 9: Bifurcation diagrams of the system Eqs. (4),(5) as a function of f with (a) $g = 1.0$ and (b) $g = 1.5$. The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0,$ and $\Omega = \omega = 6.0$.

and 8(b), the onset of chaos occurs at $f_c = 0.593751$ for $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$ and at $f_c = 0.692582$ for $\Omega = \omega = 5.5$. A comparison of Figs. (3-8) clearly indicates that as the frequency $\Omega(= \omega)$ of the parametric forces increases, the onset of chaos shifts to higher f values. Additionally, the bifurcation patterns for $g = 1.0$ and $g = 1.5$ are shown in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b). By comparing Fig. 4 with Fig. 9, the onset of chaos is observed at $f_c = 0.593751, f_c = 0.692582,$ and $f_c = 0.840934$ for $g = 0.7, g = 1.0,$ and $g = 1.5$, respectively. This demonstrates that increasing the amplitude (g) of the second parametric force leads to the suppression of chaos.

Next, we analyze the occurrence of horseshoe chaos by selecting the amplitude g as the control parameter while keeping f fixed. The bifurcation structures for $f = 0.7$ and $f = 1.0$ are shown in Figs. 10(a) and 10(b) with $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$. In Fig.8(a), for $\Omega = \omega = 5.0, g = 0.7,$ and

FIG. 10: Bifurcation diagrams of the system (4),(5) as a function of g with (a) $f = 0.7$ and (b) $f = 1.0$. The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0$, and $\Omega = \omega = 5.0$.

FIG. 11: Bifurcation diagrams of the system (4),(5) as a function of f for different values of α . The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $g = 0.7, \beta = 8.0$, and $\Omega = \omega = 6.0$.

$f = 0.7, 1.0$, the system exhibits fully chaotic behavior. However, when g is used as the control parameter, both periodic and chaotic behaviors are observed, as shown in Figs. 10(a) and 10(b). This demonstrates that chaos is suppressed due to the influence of the second parametric force. The effect of the damping strength α on the system's dynamics is illustrated in Fig. 11. The bifurcation structures for four values of $\alpha = 0.5, 0.75, 0.9, 1.0$ are presented in Figs. 11(a)-11(d). As α increases, chaos is progressively suppressed, which is evident from the corresponding figures.

4.2. Effect of two parametric forces with $\Omega \neq \omega$

In the previous section, we considered the case $\Omega = \omega$. In this section, we analyze the case $\Omega \neq \omega$ to predict the onset of chaos in the system (4),(5). Figure 12(a) shows the variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus f for $g = 1.0$, while Figure 12(b) shows the variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus g for $f = 1.0$. The other parameters are fixed at $\Omega = 9.0, \omega = 6.0, \alpha = 1.0$ and $\beta = 8.0$. In Fig. 12(a), $1/\tau_M^+$ and $1/\tau_M^-$ are both zero for $f < f_M^+ = 1.452761$ and $f < f_M^- = 0.917562$, respectively. Horseshoe chaos does not occur for $f < f_M^- = 0.917562$. For f values in the interval $f_M^- < f < f_M^+$, $M^-(\tau)$ alone oscillates, implying that horseshoe chaos can occur only in the region $x < 0$. For $f_M \geq f_M^+$, horseshoe chaos can occur in both the regions $x < 0$ and $x > 0$.

FIG. 12: (a) Variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus f with $g = 1.0$. (b) Variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus g with $f = 1.0$. The continuous curve represents the positive sign of $M(\tau)$, and the dashed curve represents the negative sign of $M(\tau)$ as given by Eq. (20). The values of the other parameters in Eq. (20) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0, \omega = 6.0$, and $\Omega = 9.0$.

These analytical results are verified in Fig. 13. Figure 13(a) shows the bifurcation diagram of the system Eqs. (4),(5), where f is used as a control parameter with $g = 1.0, \Omega = 9.0, \omega = 6.0, \alpha = 1.0$, and $\beta = 8.0$. In Fig. 13(a), regions of various dynamical behaviors of the system are plotted in the (f, x) plane, where domains of non-oscillations, periodic dynamics, and chaotic dynamics can be identified. The onset

of chaos occurs at $f_c = 1.431928$, which is almost equal to the analytical value $f_M^+ = 1.452761$ (Fig. 12(a)), indicating that the analytical results agree well with the numerical results. The

FIG. 13: (a) Bifurcation diagram of the system Eqs. (4),(5) as a function of f for $g = 1.0$. (b) Bifurcation diagram of the system (4),(5) as a function of g for $f = 1.0$. (c) Magnification of part of the bifurcation diagram shown in Fig.13(b). The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0, \omega = 6.0$, and $\Omega = 9.0$.

influence of the parameter g on the dynamics of the system (4),(5), both analytically and numerically, is also explored. The corresponding analytical and numerical results are shown in Figs. 12(b) and 13(b). Figure 12(b) shows the variation of $1/\tau_M^\pm$ versus g with $f = 1.0, \Omega = 9.0$, and $\omega = 6.0$. In Fig. 12(b), $1/\tau_M^+$ and $1/\tau_M^-$ are zero for $g < g_M^+ = 2.388126$ and $g < g_M^- =$

FIG. 14: Phase portraits of the system (4),(5) showing periodic orbits and chaotic orbits by choosing values of f and g from Figs. 13(a) and 13(b). The values of the other parameters in Eqs. (4),(5) are $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 8.0, \omega = 6.0$, and $\Omega = 9.0$.

1.983521 , respectively. Horseshoe chaos does not occur for $g < g_M^- = 1.983521$. For g in the interval $g_M^- < g < g_M^+$, $M^-(\tau)$ alone oscillates, implying that horseshoe chaos can occur only in the region $x < 0$. For $g_M \geq g_M^+$, horseshoe chaos can occur in both regions $x < 0$ and $x > 0$.

These analytical results are verified through bifurcation diagrams in Fig. 13(b) and phase portraits in Fig. 14. Figure 13(b) shows the bifurcation diagram of the system Eqs. (4),(5) when g is used as a control parameter with fixed f values. The other parameters are fixed at $\Omega = 9.0, \omega = 6.0, \alpha = 1.0$ and $\beta = 8.0$. For clarity, a magnified portion of the bifurcation diagram in Fig. 13(b) is shown in Fig. 13(c). The bifurcation structures in Figs. 13(a) and 13(b) are completely different. In Fig. 13(b), various dynamical behaviors, such as period-bubbling, reverse period-doubling bifurcation, and antimonotonicity, are observed, but these behaviors are absent in Fig. 13(a).

The onset of chaos occurs at $g_c = 2.411734$, which is nearly equal to the Melnikov threshold value $g_M = 2.388126$. The analytical results are

further verified in Fig. 14. The phase portraits of the system Eqs. (4),(5) are plotted in Fig. 14 for several values of f and g , chosen from Figs. 13(a) and 13(b) in the periodic and chaotic regions. For $f = 1.36$ (where $1/\tau_M < 0.431978$), a period-4 orbit occurs, and for $f = 1.45$ (where $1/\tau_M > 0.431978$), chaotic behavior is observed, as shown in Figs. 14(a) and 14(b). Similarly, two values of g are chosen from Fig.13(b) in the periodic and chaotic regions. The corresponding phase portraits are shown in Figs. 14(c) and 14(d). For $g = 2.4$ (where $1/\tau_M < 2.411734$), periodic behavior is observed, whereas for $g = 2.42$ (where $1/\tau_M > 2.411734$), chaotic behavior is observed.

5. Conclusions

This article presents an analysis of chaos in a linearly damped Morse oscillator subjected to two parametric forces, using both analytical and numerical techniques. By applying the Melnikov analytical method, we obtained the threshold condition for the occurrence of horseshoe chaos. We analyzed the effects of two parametric forces in both the cases where $\Omega = \omega$ and

$\Omega \neq \omega$. For both cases, threshold curves were drawn in various parameter spaces. Rich dynamical behaviors, such as period-doubling bifurcation leading to chaos, multiple coexisting attractors, and chaotic attractors, were observed in both cases. Additionally, behaviors like period-bubbling, reverse period-doubling bifurcation, and antimonotonicity were observed in the case of $\Omega \neq \omega$. For certain parametric choices, suppression and enhancement of chaos were observed due to the application of the two parametric forces. The influence of the damping strength (α) was also analyzed, with chaos suppression observed as the damping strength increased. The analytical results were confirmed through numerical simulations. In this study, standard analysis methods, such as bifurcation diagrams, phase portraits, and trajectory plots, were employed.

It is important to analyze the effect of multi-frequency excitation on the dynamics of a linearly damped Morse oscillator. This will be investigated in future.

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